

Advantages and disadvantages of using pedagogical and information - communication technologies

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Annotation

The article deals with the advantages and disadvantages of using pedagogical and information-communication technologies. Here is given the principles of in the use of pedagogical technologies in education.

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Nowadays, educational technologies are considered as one of the types of human science technologies. The main factors that actualize the problem of vocational education technologies include an increase in the amount of information and the technogenic direction of the development of modern civilization, which makes society think about how high the costs of poor-quality professional training can be. The emerging trend of the transition from the information society to the post-information society makes the statement “who owns the information owns the world” untenable. When considering the concept of didactic encyclopedia, it has already been shown how the volume of information is changing today, therefore, the ability to independently obtain the necessary information from various sources, analyze it and apply it in practical professional activity and life becomes extremely important. Initially, in pedagogy there were no differences between the concepts that today have different shades of meaning: “pedagogical technology”, -“teaching technology” and “teaching technology”. The concept of “pedagogical technology” was often used only in relation to training, and the technology itself was considered only as training using technical and audiovisual means. Today, there are various approaches to the definition of “pedagogical technology”. Most educators agree on the focus of pedagogical technology on successful outcomes. “This is a functioning system of all components of the pedagogical process, built on a scientific basis, programmed in time and space and leading to the intended results” [1], - G.K. Selevko. Among the basic principles in the use of pedagogical technologies in education, there are: the principle of nature conformity, covering aspects of considering a person in the context of nature, but also prescribing the selection of educational material, and accordingly methods and technologies, in accordance with individual (gender, temperament, character, modality, lateralization of the brain) and age characteristics of students; the principle of activity is aimed at such an organization of the learning process in which students independently acquire the necessary information from various sources and learn to use the knowledge gained in practice; the principle of technology matching the

goals and objectives - goal-setting is an important stage, both in the design of the training session and in the selection of pedagogical technologies. It is important that the lessons formulated by the teaching purpose can be fully realized through the pedagogical technology chosen by him; the principle of systematicity consisting in the regularity of the use of one or another pedagogical technology to achieve a guaranteed result; the principle of culture-building implying the correspondence of pedagogical technologies to other pedagogical means used by the teacher. Insufficient attention on the part of the teacher to these principles strengthens the didactic risk of violating the holistic learning process, which can be expressed in overloading students with information and various activities, turning the learning process into shows, students' refusal to comply with the teacher's requirements. Modern technical means: computers, laptops, tablets, communicators, smartphones and other gadgets have firmly entered our lives, because they were originally created in order to facilitate and even improve it. They allow you to save time and travel the world without leaving your home. The development of technology has led all of these electronic devices to the masses. Psychologists say that the first thing to start with when there are signs of dependence on the Internet, a gadget or a computer is to shift the focus of his attention to another object, for example, study. In this case, it is not necessary to resort to the help of a tutor, costly additional courses. Parents should simply pay great attention to their child, limiting the possibilities of using the Internet and gadgets for games or communication on social networks. You should not completely prohibit the use of Internet resources or take away a cell phone from a child, you must make it clear to the child that these things should be resorted to but necessary, and not devote all their free time to them. The need may also be associated with the acquisition of new knowledge. If, when restricting a child's access to gadgets, it is worth slowing down and looking for another rational way out of this situation. In addition to aggression, there are other signs that suggest computer addiction. This is a deterioration or a lack of desire to break away from work at a computer or gadget; loss of ability to control time spent on an electronic device; termination of fulfillment of domestic obligations in favor of a game or work at a computer; transition from any topic in the conversation to the subject of computer hardware, software, games; neglect of real communication with friends, isolation. In addition to the symptoms associated with a violation in behavior, abnormalities in the physical condition, suffering from computer addiction, can be diagnosed: more frequent headache attacks; worsening sleep and insomnia; visual impairment and visual impairment; a feeling of back pain. From the above, we can conclude that the use of pedagogical technologies causes double feelings. On the one hand, this leads to a disruption in the process of training and education of students, on the other hand, it makes it possible to fulfill your needs and reveal your abilities.

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